

Manik Sarkar and His Chronicle

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ABSTRACT

Manik Sarkar is the past 9th Chief Minister of the north-eastern Indian declares of Tripura. He is extensively considered as the 'largely truthful' and 'mainly unsoiled' chief minister in the state. He is an opinionated constituent of the Communist Party of India (Marxist). This tabloid as glowing efforts to discuss the review of motivated and stimulate subsequently premature life, delicate life, opinionated career, deprivers Chief Minister.

Keywords: Chief Minister, Communist, Political, Social

INTRODUCTION

Manik Sarkar is an Indian Communist representative. He was affirmed in as the Chief Minister of Tripura for the 3rd successive expression in March 2008. He initial befall the Chief Minister of the eastern declare 1998 in Tripura. Manik Sarkar is the greatest allocation CM of the state. He feels right to the (Marxist) {CPM} Communist party of India and a member of its fifteen members taking sides. He was nominated to the circumstances Legislative Assembly beginning Dhanpur in West Tripura. That state is the only India everywhere the CPM led Left facade is in supremacy. In the 2013 congregation elections, he becomes the chief minister of Tripura for the successive fourth instance. [1]

PREMATURE LIFE

Manik Sarkar

He was born on January 22, 1949 in Radhakishorepur, Udaipur, and Tripura into core-division ancestors. Manik Sarkar's tend, Anjali Sarkar, was a command hand in Tripura whereas his priest, Amulya Sarkar, was a tailor. He was a contender of the Students' amalgamation of India during his intellectual existence at Maharaja Bir Bikram College, from where he graduated amid a Bachelor of Commerce degree since College in Agartala, Tripura. At some stage in his 1st year at the institution convenient come the disorderly epoch of the victuals faction of 1967, confrontation adjacent to the procedure of the Congress supervision of Tripura, and he throw himself hurried into the interrelated learner efforts. His energetic liability in this accumulation progress led him to unite the Communists. Due to his untimely supporting disclosure, he is addition became the common escriptoire of the Maharaja Bir Bikram College learner amalgamation and was also prepared the Sub- Head of the Students' confederacy of India. Manik Sarkar' in 1972, at the premature age of 23, he united the Declare Committee of the Communist (Marxist) Party. [2]

DELICATE LIFE

He was wedded is Panchali Bhattacharya and his worked in Central Social Welfare

Manik Sarkar

Panchali Bhattacharya

Boad. Manik Sarkar comprises a renowned reputa as a chief minister as he is the separate skull of the regime between every the states in India who individual no residence or car of his own. Manik Sarkar mate has refusal delicate precautions sentinel and do not use several manner of transportation that is fanatical in provision of the chief minister and his ancestors. [3]

OPINIONATED CAREER

Flag of CPIM

- Manik Sarkar tied the Marxist Communist Party at the age of 19 in 1968.
- Manik Sarkar tied the state committee of the Marxist Communist Party at the age of 23 in 1972.
- He initiated into the state secretariat of CPIM at the age of 29 in 1978.
- He was designated Member of the Legislative Assembly from the Agartala Constituency at the age of 31 in 1980.
- He was nominated to Assembly from Krishnanagar, Agartala, at the age of 34 in 1983.
- He was appointed the state secretary of the CPIM at the age of 44 in 1993.
- The Chief Minister of Tripura state in 1998 to 2018 successfully stands in 20 year. [4][5]

DEPRIVERS CHIEF MINISTER

Manik Sarkar's was a distinctive peculiarity of residence in Tripura's Chief Minister. He bestows in whole representative income to his party and capture only Rs 5,000 per month as his grants. Manik Sarkar hence portrays the majority smallest quantity of salary

between the intact CM in India. He was a habitually considered as the 'Cleanest and Poorest' Chief Minister in India. He invariable and his opponents sleet him as a corruption free stature. [6]

CONCLUSION

Manik Sarkar is the greatest Chief Minister in state of Tripura. Also discuss India is a different state and different CM's they are follows in different thoughts and policy. The purpose of this study is people selected the truthful and genuine persons on the elections.

“We want people to live without fear and the state police will always be there to protect them” – Manik Sarkar [7]

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